

Studies on mixed ligand complexes of oxovanadium(IV) and titanium(III) with organic dibasic acid and heterocyclic amines

M. Saidul Islam^{a*} and M. Ashraful Alam^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi, Bangladesh

^bDepartment of Chemistry, B. I. T., Rajshahi, Bangladesh

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A number of new mixed ligand complexes of oxovanadium(IV) and titanium(III) containing tetrachlorophthalic acid and nitrogen-containing heterocyclic bases have been synthesized. The complexes have the composition [VO(tcpa).L], [VO(tcpa).L'₂], [Ti(tcpa).L] and [Ti(tcpa).L'₂], where L = bidentate ligands, L' = monodentate ligands and tcpa = tetrachlorophthalic acid. All the complexes are found to be octahedral.

Metal salts of phthalic acid¹, phthalic anhydride² and heterocyclic amines³ possess various biological activities. There are reports on the metal complexes of phthalic acid⁴. The thermodynamic functions of mixed ligand chelate of oxovanadium(IV) with dicarboxylic acids have been determined⁵. We report herein the synthesis of some new complexes of oxovanadium(IV) and titanium(III) containing tetrachlorophthalic acid as primary ligand and heterocyclic amines as secondary ligands.

Results and Discussion

The formation of the complexes can be shown by the following reactions :

where, L = 2-aminopyridine, bipyridine, *o*-phenanthroline, 8-hydroxyquinoline and benzedine; L' = quinoline, isoquinoline, pyridine, 2-picoline and 4-picoline.

The analytical data (Table 1) are in good agreement with the proposed formulae of the complexes. The molar conductance values (Table 1) indicate that the complexes Sl. nos. 1-6, 8, 9 are non-electrolyte and Sl. nos. 7, 10-18 are 1 : 1 electrolyte⁶.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Sl. no	Compd **/ (Colour)	Metal % · Found/(Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Mol cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} B.M
1.	[VO(tcpa)(bipy)] (Green)	9.86 (9.98)	265d	4.2	1.84
2.	[VO(tcpa)(2-apy)] (Green)	11.28 (11.39)	270d	15.8	1.68
3.	[VO(tcpa)(phen)] (Greenish)	9.12 (9.27)	200	5.2	1.77
4.	[VO(tcpa)(benz)] (Green)	9.08 (9.21)	>300	6.2	1.88
5.	[VO(tcpa)(qn) ₂] (Green)	8.00 (8.12)	>300	6.3	1.73
6.	[VO(tcpa)(iqn) ₂] (Black)	8.02 (8.12)	>300	5.2	1.65
7.	K[VO(tcpa)(oxin)] (Brown)	10.0 (10.23)	240	64.4	1.66
8.	[VO(tcpa)(py) ₂] (Greenish)	9.49 (9.66)	>300	8.4	1.68
9.	[VO(tcpa)(4-pic) ₂] (Green)	9.00 (9.17)	240d	9.5	1.84
10.	K[Ti(tcpa) ₂ (bipy)] (Offwhite)	5.47 (5.67)	255	82.3	1.79
11.	K[Ti(tcpa) ₂ (2-apy)] (Offwhite)	6.00 (6.13)	290d	88.7	1.77
12.	K[Ti(tcpa) ₂ (phen)] (Offwhite)	5.42 (5.51)	270	79.2	1.64
13.	K[Ti(tcpa) ₂ (benz)] (Offwhite)	5.34 (5.64)	280d	66.2	1.74
14.	K[Ti(tcpa) ₂ (qn) ₂] (Offwhite)	5.00 (5.06)	285d	71.8	1.84

Table-1 (contd.)

15.	K[Ti(tcpa) ₂ (iqn) ₂] (Offwhite)	5.06 (4.94)	295d	73.8	1.79
16.	K ₂ [Ti(tcpa) ₂ (oxin)] (Yellow)	5.46 (5.60)	300d	162.6	1.68
17.	K[Ti(tcpa) ₂ (4-pic) ₂] (Offwhite)	5.44 (5.47)	>300	62.3	1.64
18.	K[Ti(tcpa) ₂ (py) ₂] (Offwhite)	3.49 (3.66)	280d	84.4	1.92

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**tcpa = C₈H₂O₄Cl₄ (deprotonated), bipy = C₁₀H₈N₂, 2-apy = C₅H₆N₂, oxinH = C₉H₆NO, phen = C₁₂H₈N₂, benz = C₁₂H₁₂N₂, qn or iqn = C₉H₇N, py = C₅H₅N and 4-pic = C₆H₇N.

d = Decompose.

The strong bands at 1650 (C=O) and 1400 cm⁻¹ (C-O) in the ir spectrum of free tetrachlorophthalic acid shifted to ~1590–1630 and 1380–1435 cm⁻¹ respectively in the spectra of the complexes, indicating the coordination of tetrachlorophthalic acid through its carboxylate anions⁷. The expected ν_{O-H} bands due to 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxinH) were absent in the spectra of their respective complexes (Sl. nos. 7, 16), revealing that 8-hydroxyquinoline acts as uninegative bidentate ligand coordinating through the oxygen and nitrogen donors. Further, the presence of M-O bonding is evident from the appearance of ν_{M-O} mode at 360–430 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes⁸. The oxovanadium complexes display bands at 960–985 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{V-O} mode⁹. The complexes Sl. nos. 2 and 11 show two ν_{NH_2} bands at ~3260 and ~3180 cm⁻¹, which are significantly lower than the free ligand (aminopyridine) bands (~3400 and ~3000 cm⁻¹). The characteristic ring vibrations of the heterocyclic amines at 1400–1600 cm⁻¹ show significant changes on complexation¹⁰, which could not be distinguished because of overlapping with $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-O} stretching bands. The in-plane and out-of-plane ring deformation modes of heterocyclic amines at ~500 and ~700 cm⁻¹ respectively, undergo positive shift in mixed ligand complexes, confirming their coordination through nitrogen¹¹. The presence of M-N bonding is evident from the appearance of ν_{M-N} mode at 290–350 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes¹².

The observed effective magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of the complexes are given in Table 1. The μ_{eff} values of the oxovanadium(IV) and titanium(III) complexes (1.66–1.94 B.M.) indicate their paramagnetic nature with one unpaired electron¹³, thereby suggesting paramagnetic octahedral geometry.

The electronic spectra of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes gave four bands (I, II, III, IV) at 17700–18115, 22935–23584, 31645–32362 and 38610–39525 cm⁻¹. The first two bands correspond to the ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transitions and the latter two to charge transfer bands. All

these are typical for octahedral oxovanadium(IV) complexes¹⁴. The titanium(III) complexes gave only one band at 19607–20408 cm⁻¹, which is obviously derived from the transition ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ for an O_h symmetry¹⁵.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam sp3300 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (nujol) on a LKB Biochrom Ultrascope 4053 spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurement was carried out on a Johnson Mathey magnetic susceptibility balance at 30°. Conductivity measurement of 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ solutions of the complexes in DMSO at 30° was made on a WPACM 35 instrument using a dip-type cell with platinized electrodes. Melting and decomposition points were determined on an electrothermal apparatus. Vanadium and titanium were estimated gravimetrically. C, H and N were analyzed at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Center, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, India. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade (E. Merck and B.D.H.).

Oxovanadium(IV) complexes : A mixture of ethanolic solutions (20 ml each) of vanadyl sulfate pentahydrate (0.004 mol) and of tetrachlorophthalic acid (0.004 mol) was refluxed for ~0.5 h on a steam-bath. An ethanolic solution (20 ml) of L (0.004 mol) or L' (0.008 mol) or a solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline [prepared by mixing 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.004 mol) with KOH (0.004 mol) in ethanol (20 ml)] was then added to it with stirring. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for ~0.5 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed successively with ethanol and ether, then dried and stored under reduced pressure over silica gel.

Titanium(III) complexes : A mixture of ethanolic solutions (20 ml each) of the metal(III) chloride (0.004 mol) and tetrachlorophthalic acid (0.004 mol) was refluxed for ~0.5 h on a steam-bath. An ethanolic solution (20 ml) of L (0.004 mol) or L' (0.008 mol) or a solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline [prepared by mixing 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.004 mol) with KOH (0.004 mol) in ethanol (20 ml)] was added to it with stirring followed by careful addition of an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of KOH (0.008 mol). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for ~0.5 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed successively with ethanol and ether, then dried and stored under reduced pressure over silica gel.

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